

ADDICTION AS A SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. *The article provides information about the socio-psychological problems of virtual addiction.*

Keywords: *globalization process, Internet, addiction, ideological problems, computer games, frustration, psychological-pedagogical influence.*

Today, which is called the process of globalization, computer technologies and the Internet have rapidly entered our lives and have become one of its integral components. The Internet has become one of the most important tools for solving ideological problems. However, at the same time, along with its opportunities, it should not be overlooked that there are threats and dangers of the world global information network that must be clearly imagined.

Internet addiction or Internet addiction is an uncontrollable urge, desire, and excessive use of the Internet. Internet addiction is not listed as a mental disorder in the 5th edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5), a nosological system used in the United States since 2013, but it was developed by the World Health Organization in 1989 and revised in 2022. included in the 11th edition of the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Problems under the category of mental illness and addiction.

As a result of the rapid development of information technologies, the number of people who use computers and gadgets (devices) in their work activities, and become addicted to the Internet, computer games, virtual world, and social networks, is increasing. Considering that young people are primarily interested in news in all fields, the majority of current information technology addicts are between the ages of 10 and 30.

In Western countries, they officially use the term "pathological use of devices". Today, this term and phrase (pathological use of devices) is used to refer to people who continuously use devices for purposes other than social purposes, despite the fact that experts have not yet formed a unanimous opinion about psychological dependence on the Internet and computers.

In general, addiction to modern information technology can be manifested in two forms:

- internet addiction (internet addiction);
- excessive indulgence in computer games.

There are common and specific aspects of both these views. Common features of computer or phone addiction include a number of interrelated psychological and physiological symptoms.

Psychological symptoms are:

- feeling euphoric or comfortable in front of the computer;
- inability to stop working with a computer;
- increasing time spent in front of the computer;
- decreasing attention to family and friends, people;
- observation of feelings of depression and bitterness in places other than the computer;
- giving false information about one's work to employers and family members;
- the existence of problems related to work or study activities.

Physical (physiological) signs include:

- carpal tunnel syndrome (damage of nerve fibers in hands and fingers as a result of muscle strain);

- dry eyes;
- sometimes severe headache;
- shoulder, back pain;
- not eating on time, sometimes skipping meals;
- non-observance of personal hygiene rules;
- sleep disturbance.

Pathological use of the computer may not lead a person to the bottom like alcoholism or drug addiction (chemical dependence, addiction) in general. However, it cannot be denied that it has a negative impact on the development of a person's personality.

When it comes to addiction, it is necessary to analyze the impact of computer games on a person's psyche. According to researchers who interviewed some addicts and their parents and relatives, high levels of anxiety and depression are noticeable in addicts. Relatives of addicts claim that they are extremely irritable, angry, and emotionally unstable.

Computer game addicts feel a constant need for gaming, but at the same time suffer from the inability to satisfy this need because they are constantly in a state of frustration. A description of the mental characteristics of addicts in the virtual (imaginary) and real world helps to understand this abnormality and paradox.

According to this description (which, by the way, is favored by many addicts), the problem can be illuminated as follows: the fact that addicts are constantly in a state of frustration and depression in the real world causes them to experience high levels of anxiety and depression. This was determined using the clinical-psychopathological method. It is more difficult to determine what processes are going on in their minds during computer games, because any distraction or attempt to distract from the game means leaving the virtual, imaginary world. However, from conversations with addicts, it is known that during the game, their mood is much higher, because at this time positive emotions increase. Positive feelings associated with mood elevation are also associated with anticipatory enjoyment of computer gaming. However, after the game, that is, after leaving the virtual world, they return to the same depressed mood.

Most addicts are people who do not adapt well to social life. They often have problems related to household, family, work, and representatives of the opposite sex. Therefore, addicts find the real world boring, unpleasant, and dangerous. This is the reason why people tend to live in a virtual world where everything is allowed, where the rules are set by themselves. Logically speaking, leaving the virtual world is an unpleasant situation for the addict, because he is forced to return to a world he does not want, he is again depressed, he feels unpleasant in every way. Therefore, the reason for bad mood in addicts is, on the one hand, the presence of a constant need for computer games, and on the other hand, the inability to satisfy this need. Another reason for their deviations in the emotional-emotional sphere is that they subjectively realize the futility of their activities (computer games) and feel their helplessness in the face of psychological addiction. This refers to a kind of cognitive dissonance, that is, a discrepancy between the socially acceptable life and the addict's life. In other words, addicts live in a state of constant self-denial.

Although this aspect may seem strange, the truth is that most ardent fans of computer games seriously consider their actions. Thoughts like "I had so much to do, and I played on the computer all night" torment them. For some addicts, computer games can act as psychological protection.

As noted, in most cases, addicts try to overcome the disadaptation (inability to adapt) in the real situation by entering the role of computer characters in the virtual world. The addict strives to find his virtual "I", because this "I" is stronger, smarter, can use weapons, allows him to buy what he wants. But a person does not forget that he lives in the real world, so even the division of the individual consciousness can be observed.

From this point of view, giving up the super-powerful image in the virtual world and returning to one's "I" is not something that satisfies addicts.

When using the Internet, it is appropriate to focus on its positive aspects, such as the development of children's abilities and mental capabilities, rather than the negative ones.

It is known that during adolescence, the teenager's "I" is formed again. His attitude to others, especially to himself, direction of interests, values changes dramatically. His attention to his personality will increase. During adolescence, individual egocentrism reaches its highest level compared to other periods. During this period, a teenager becomes one who puts his personality above others and builds more for himself. During this period, both boys and girls do not just imitate adults, but literally control their behavior, their behavior, dress, pay attention to their appearance, and do makeup. During this period, a minor negative remark about the appearance and personality of a teenager can be the basis for him to experience serious negative experiences.

During adolescence, which is often described as "transient", the body and nervous system cannot yet cope with severe and long-term effects. Therefore, in such cases, the nervous system can go into a state of inhibition. This is the body's own defense mechanism. The main activity of this period is studying, and it is important for a teenager not only to acquire knowledge and skills, but also to form professions, beliefs, needs and motives, and social communication skills. The Internet is of great importance in this process nowadays.

The response to the effect of information, the reaction to receiving it, is different in people. So to speak, it can be said that the "weakest" layer in terms of information and information's effect on the psyche is the youth.

Currently, a new branch of science - information (computer) psychology is developing rapidly.

In this direction, the following problems are studied:

- a person's fear of ever-improving computer technologies, information flow (computerophobia);
- a person's desire to communicate not with people, but with the computer and its means - "infomania";
- fatigue of people during computer work;
- avoid becoming too attached to the computer.

Computer and Internet addiction is a gradual, step-by-step process, like an addiction. There are three stages of this disease:

at the first stage, they often rush to the global network, the Internet, to retreat from problems, to forget about them.

In the second stage, it is noticeable that it is very difficult for a person to disconnect from the Internet. That is, at this stage, the amount of time spent on the Internet increases more and more.

The third stage is complete addiction, in which the time a person spends on the Internet seems to decrease, if not more than before. This can be compared to the increase in the amount of narcotic substance taken by a drug addict. This situation can be explained as follows.

The formation of a person's ideas about himself depends on the period of his youth, and usually during adolescence, the image of "I" is not fully formed. In such cases, virtual, imaginary characters help to meet the needs of the teenager in this regard. A person who cannot fully express himself in society tries to do so in virtual reality, in an imaginary space. This situation occurs in internet addiction. A person who does not have problems with communication, communication and socialization does not feel the need for activities in the virtual world.

Psychological-pedagogical impact on the representatives of the younger generation, supporting them psychologically-pedagogically is important in a number of aspects. First of all, it should be noted that young people are the main driving force and perspective of all societies. As the formation of the personality of young people coincides with the time of complex political, social, and economic changes in the whole world, the support of the older generation will certainly be necessary for their proper upbringing. Providing the necessary psychological and pedagogical advice and support to boys and girls, forming appropriate behavioral skills in them, directing their energy to themselves, protecting their minds from the influence of destructive ideas is one of the important factors of ensuring the safety of the individual, state and society.

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